

National Education Policy (NEP) 2020: Opportunities and Challenges in Higher Education

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Abstract: Education is essential and fundamental tool for achieving human potential and promoting national development. It is the key to economic development, social justice, scientific advancement, cultural preservation and helps for national integration. National education policy 2020 is the first education policy of 21st century. This policy is aligned to 2030 agenda for sustainable development and aims to transform India into a vibrant Knowledge society and global knowledge superpower by making both school and college education more holistic, flexible, and multidisciplinary. The National Education Policy 2020 has many opportunities viz; accessibility, quality, and accountability along with gross enrolment ratio to be raised from 22 percent to 50 percent by 2035. Though this policy has various opportunities but on the other this policy is facing some challenges too. The challenges such as poor inclusive knowledge of students and teachers, commercialization, and corruption in higher education, rigid attitudes of the stake holders, poor learning outcomes, lack of research and innovation etc.

Key words: Higher education, New Policy-2020, Opportunities and challenges

Introduction: Education is the most essential tool for everyone to become successful in life. This is fundamental for achieving full human potential and thereby promoting national development. It is the foundation stone of the nation which plays a significant role in the development and growth of the citizens and the country. Education is also the true path for a better future and is one of the most powerful tools for transforming the whole nation into empowered society. Education is a key factor to economic development, social justice, scientific advancement, cultural preservation and helps for national integration.

Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam said, “the purpose of education is to make better human beings with skill and expertise in enlightening human beings”. Education system needs to make students as learners, scholars, researchers, innovators, and trainers. In ancient India; both formal and informal education system was prevalent. Indigenous education was imparted in temples, at home, Pathashalas, Gurukulas etc. There were the erudite people in villages and temples who used to guide young children in imbibing pious ways of life. Students went for Viharas and Universities for more knowledge and teaching was largely oral, and students remembered and meditated upon what was taught in the classes.

In ancient India; the aim of education was not just the acquisition of knowledge as preparation for life or beyond schooling i.e. for the complete realization and liberation of the self. The world-famous institutions of ancient India viz; Nalanda, Takshashila, Vallabhi, Vikramshila etc., set the highest standards of multidisciplinary teaching and research. The Indian education system produced great scholars like, Susruta, Chakrapani Datta,

Charak, Madahva, Chanakya, Bhaskaracharya, Brahmagupta, Aryabhata, Varahamihira, Panini, Nagarjun, Patanjali, Pingala, Gautama, Sankardev, Mytrei, Thiruvalluvar and Gargi etc., who made great contributions to the world knowledge in various fields such as Culture, Yoga, Engineering, Philosophy, Science and Surgery, Medical field, Astronomy, Mathematics, Navigation etc.

NEP 2020 is the first education policy of 21st century. It was formulated by the Government of India (GOI) to promote education amongst Indian people. This policy is aligned to the 2030 agenda for sustainable development and aims to transform India into a vibrant knowledge society and global knowledge super power by making both school and college education more holistic, flexible and multidisciplinary; which is suited to 21 century.

National Education Policy 2020:

The National Education Policy of 2020 is India's 3rd Education Policies after the policy of 1968 and 1986. National Education Policy 2020; replaces the National Education Policy of 1986. The draft NEP was submitted in 2019 by a panel led by former ISRO chief executive Padma-Vibhushan Dr. Krishnaswamy Kasturirangan. The NEP was later launches by central cabinet of India and the same was approved by the “National Education Policy” on 29th July 2020. This policy aims to flagstone for transformational improvements in Indi's schools and higher educational institutions and striving to transform India into a ‘Vibrant Knowledge Society.’ This policy also emphasizes on promoting multilingualism i.e., no language will be imposed on any student. NEP 2020 which intended to transform our nation sustainably into an equitable and vibrant knowledge society, by providing high quality education to all. India has always been a destination

for learners all around the world and for that, it is called as the land of learning.

The National Education Policy 2020 aims to transform education, keeping the learner at the centre. This policy focusses on the holistic development of students by ensuring access, relevance, quality, equity, and strong foundational learning. The Modern Higher Education System in the 21st century is constituted a new approach to learning from online education to skill development platform of education. Grading system as well as the use of educational technology in the classrooms is introduced for achieving 100 percent youth and adult literacy with holistic development of learners. In India; after a gap of 34 years, there is a change happened in the education; with the introduction of New Education Policy. This Policy lays emphasis on the development of creative potential of everyone in all its richness and complexity. It is based on both foundational skills (basic literacy, numeracy, and transferable skills) and cognitive skills (perception, attention, memory, and logical reasoning) such as problem solving, critical thinking, development of emotional and social skills i.e., soft skills, team work, leadership qualities etc. According to **Prime Minister Narendra Modi** “the new education policy focusses on learning instead of studying beyond the curriculum to focus on critical thinking.” The policy 2020 focusses on the quality rather than quantity. National education Policy laid emphasis on student centric learning, creativity, and skill development. New Education Policy 2020 emphasis on gross enrolment ratio (GER) in higher education to be raised to 50 percent and academic bank of credits to be made to facilitate transfer of credits for lateral admission to other institutions. A single overcharging umbrella body for the entire higher education system, fostering a strong research culture and building research capacity across higher education. Affiliation of colleges is to be phased out in 15 years.

It is rightly said that, higher education is an important aspect of education system in deciding the economy, technology adoption, social status, and healthy human behaviour in every country. This policy transforming India; sustainably into an equitable and vibrant knowledge society by providing high quality education to all, and there by making India a global knowledge superpower. As per the New Educational Policy; no language or subject will be imposed on any student. The curriculum and pedagogy of our educational institutions must develop a deep sense of respect towards the fundamental duties and values of the constitution and conscious awareness of one’s roles and responsibilities in a changing the national scenario.

The New Education Policy 2020 focusses on quality, equity, affordability, accountability and aims to address various gaps existing in the Indian Education System. Through this policy, India is expected to achieve sustainable development goal of 2030 by ensuring equitable and inclusive quality education.

Objectives of the Study: Following are the important objectives of the study are:

1. To highlight the brief Historical background of Indian Education
2. To throw light on the concept of new educational policy-2020 and higher education
3. To explore the opportunities and challenges of higher education and NEP
4. These papers also extract the gap between policy and practice in higher education system

Opportunities of NEP- 2020:

The new education policy 2020 focusses on many opportunities such as accessibility and quality of education and increase in gross enrolment ratio in higher education to be raised from 22 percent to 50 percent by 2035.

1. NEP-2020 focusses on five pillars viz., Access, Quality, Equity, Affordability and Accountability and transform India into a vibrant knowledge hub
2. Flexible UG courses with multiple entries and exits viz; after One year of UG programme (academic recognition is Certificate), after Two years of UG programme (Advanced Diploma), after Three years of UG programme (Bachelor’s Degree), after Four years of UG programme (Bachelor is with honour).
3. NEP envisages achieving equitable and inclusive quality education for all
4. Special Education Zones (SEZ) will be created for disadvantaged categories and regions which will make higher education opportunities more accessible for students
5. National Education Policy focuses on inter-disciplinary learning
6. The new policy emphasises on systematic and institutional improvements in governance and promotion of multidisciplinary academics and research in higher education
7. Policy 2020 channelizes; students focus towards practical skills and vocational learning
8. Students have flexibility to choose subjects and broader options to learn
9. Gross Enrolment Ratio in Higher education to be raised to 50 percent by 2035
10. National Educational Policy 2020; has emphasised the use of technology in teaching-learning process

Challenges Related to NEP- 2020: Though the New education policy contains opportunities but has have some challenges too. The challenges such as

poor inclusive knowledge of students and teachers, commercialization, and corruption in higher education, rigid attitudes of the stake holders, poor learning outcomes, lack of research and innovation etc.

1. Poor inclusive knowledge of students and teaching quality of teachers
2. Teaching in mother tongue language will be challenging as India has 22 scheduled languages and innumerable dialects
3. No proper value-based education and poor women's education
4. Commercialization and corruption in higher education
5. Rigid attitudes of the stake holders i.e., Teachers, Students, Parents, and Management
6. Lack of teachers and institutional independence to do new things for attracting a greater number of students
7. Poor learning outcomes and development of cognitive skills of students
8. Lack of access to higher education, especially in the most economically disadvantaged regions has resulted in less gross enrolment ratio (GER)
9. There is a persistent mismatch between the Knowledge and skills imparted and the jobs available in the market
10. Lack of research and innovation at many colleges and universities
11. Lack of teaching and learning materials and poor quality of training
12. Lack of research funding, low level of governance and leadership
13. Scarcity of teaching aids and technology and need to create a large pool of trained teachers

Conclusion: It is fact that; well designed, well-defined and comprehensive education policy is essential at college and university levels. It is an important aspect in deciding the economy, social status, technology adoption and healthy human behaviour for every nation. The present-day education system has a lot to learn from the ancient education system of India. Hence, the stress is being laid on connecting learning to the world outside the school. In higher education, the National Education Policy 2020 focuses on inter-disciplinary learning which is very welcome step. The Policy is both local and global in its outlook and intent.

Today educationalists recognise the importance of multilingual and multicultural education, thereby connecting the ancient and the traditional knowledge with contemporary learning. Encouraging merit-based admissions with free-ships and scholarships, merit and research based continuous performance as faculty members and merit based proven leaders in regulating bodies. Strict monitoring accreditation based on self-declaration is expected to fulfil its objective by 2030.

Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam had said “enlightened citizenship has 3 components viz; education with vale system, creating economic prosperity and religion transforming into spiritual force. The new policy has stride in the right direction and it focusses on the holistic development of students by ensuring access, relevance, equity, quality, and strong foundational leaning. The policy lays emphasis on 4 key areas of reforms viz., improving quality of learning in all levels of education, curricular changes to build strong foundational skills, shift in the ways of assessment and need for systematic transformation.

NEP 2020 is expected to put India on the track to attain goal of 2030 agenda for sustainable development by ensuring quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities. The famous statement of **Nelson Mandela** goes like, “Destroying nation does not require the use of atomic bombs or the use of long-range missiles. It only requires lowering the quality of education and allowing cheating in the examinations by the students” In the National Education Policy 2020; there are more good aspects rather less appreciative ones. NEP will prove beneficial to both students and the education sector. The success of NEP 2020 and the pace of its implementation depends on how successfully the Government, Universities and Colleges can tide over the practical challenges facing it.

No doubt, the Government of India took a giant leap forward by announcing its new education policy 2020, almost three decades after the last revision was made to policy in 1986. National education policy 2020 brings in ambitious changes that could transform the education system by only its proper implementation and execution.

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